
PROGRAM

Wed, Nov 12	Thu, Nov 13	Fri, Nov 14	Sat, Nov 15
-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------

Hall A**08:00-09:00****Oral presentations of selected abstracts**

09:00-09:30**KEY NOTE LECTURE****Lifetime journey and paradigm shift in breast cancer understanding and treatment***Alberto Costa*

09:30-10:30**Special panel:
Innovating together: when research meets clinical practice***Moderator: TBD*

Introduction*TBD*

Panel discussion*TBD*

10:30-10:40**Coffee break**

10:40-11:35**Scientific projects in Serbia***Moderators: Ivana Božović Spasojević, Radmila Janković*

10:40-10:55**2023-2026: Detection and quantification of residual disease in patients with high-risk and advanced melanoma as a marker of therapy response and prognosis (ReDiMEL); PRIZMA; Fond za nauku Republike Srbije (Beograd)***Lidija Kandolf*

10:55-11:10**2023-2026: Advancing REversible immunocapture toward SCALable EV purification (RESCALE-EV); PRIZMA; Fond za nauku Republike Srbije (Beograd)**

2025-2028: EXPANDING the value of Extracellular Vesicles as carriers of biomarker and therapy in precision healthcare (EXPAND-EV); Horizont Evropa, MSCA Staff Exchange; Evropska lecture komisija (Brisel, Belgija)

Milica Popović

11:10-11:25

MiNe2Brain, Development of an innovative platform consisting of lipid- polymer hybrid nanoparticles and microneedles for targeted brain delivery of novel GABAkinases favored by reverse transport; DIJASPORA 2023; Fond za nauku Republike Srbije (Beograd)

Miroslav Savić

11:25-11:35

Discussion

11:35-12:25

**Special panel
Artificial intelligence: reshaping the landscape and horizons of oncology**

Moderators: Mirjan Nadrljanski, Nada Santrač

11:35-11:50

AI in screening

Mirjan Nadrljanski

11:50-12:10

AI in surgical oncology

Pedro Gouveia

12:10-12:25

Discussion: Steps towards clinical implementation in Serbia

Mihailo Jovanović

12:25-13:10

Sponsored symposium MSD

13:10-14:10

Lunch

14:10-16:00

When Cancer Comes Early: New Perspectives on Young-Onset Malignancies

Moderators: Jelena Spasić, Ivana Božović Spasoiević

14:10-14:25

Rising Tide: Tackling the Challenge of Early-Onset Cancers in breast cancer

Ivana Božović Spasojević

14:25-14:35

Discussion

14:35-14:50

Rising Tide: Tackling the Challenge of Early-Onset Cancers in lung cancer

Jelena Spasić

14:50-15:00

Discussion

15:00-15:15

Rising Tide: Tackling the Challenge of Early-Onset Cancers in colorectal cancer

Neda Nikolić

15:15-15:25

Discussion

15:25-15:40

Rising Tide: Tackling the Challenge of Early-Onset Cancers in gynecological cancers

Marta Nerone

15:40-15:50

Discussion

15:50-16:50

Sponsored symposium Amicus

16:50-17:00

Coffee break

17:00-18:40

**From 3D-CRT, IMRT, and VMAT to Proton and Hadron Therapy:
Shaping the Future of Radiotherapy**

Moderators: Marina Nikitović, Tatjana Stanojković

17:00-17:15

Modern radiotherapy - what does the future offer us

Aleksandar Stepanović

17:15-17:30

Advancing Cancer Care Through Particle Therapy

Angelica Facoetti

17:30-17:45

The Slovenian proton therapy project

Mark Pleško

17:45-18:00

Proton therapy - clinical aspects

Jelena Bokun

18:00-18:15

RadExIORSBoost Exploring Individual Radiosensitivity: A Voyage Through RNA and miRNA Universe

Nina Petrović

18:15-18:30

The Role of Tumor-Derived Exosomal miRNAs in the Tumor Microenvironment and Circulating Cell Signaling

Ivan Jovanović

18:30-18:40

Discussion

Be part of the 62nd Oncology Congress

Discover the latest advances in oncology – secure your place now.

Register now

[Learn more](#)

[Home](#)

[Program](#) ▾

[About](#) ▾

[Sponsors](#)

[Contact](#)

Copyright © 2025 Oncology | Powered by [Inovativne Medicinske Terapije](#)